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Annotation: *The article provides a scientific analysis of corruption, which is one of the most dangerous evils of society in various ways, and the causes and conditions of its occurrence. The experience of foreign countries and recommendations for improving the mechanism for identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions of violations were also put forward.*

Keywords: *Corruption Mechanism of Measures to Ensure the Rule of Law.*

There are many flaws that can torture society in different ways. The most dangerous of them for the state and the people is corruption. This harmful phenomenon occurs in all countries, large and small, rich and poor [1]. The term "corruption" is derived from the Latin word "corruptio", which means "corruption" and "bribery". These two words define the essence of corruption. Corruption is a social phenomenon that threatens the country's economy. This is manifested in corruption. However, "corruption" is a broader concept than "bribery", and bribery is at its core.

Corruption poses a serious threat to the rule of law, democracy, human rights, trust in government, governance, equality and social justice, healthy competition in the economy and hinders economic growth, hinders the formation and development of democratic and civil society institutions. trying to write.

Corruption is certainly not a scourge that has emerged today, it has existed since ancient times. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle said, "In any state system, through laws and other decrees, work must be organized in such a way that officials are not allowed to enrich themselves illegally."

According to the sources that have come down to us, in the 24th century BC, the ruler of Babylon, Urikagin, issued a decree severely punishing his court officials for bribery in order to curb their lust, but he could not stop them from committing corruption crimes.

In the Middle Ages, a judge who took a bribe in Sweden had two fingers of his right hand cut off.

The French thinker Charles Montesquieu said that "it is known from centuries of experience that any person with any authority has a tendency to abuse it and walks in that direction until he achieves a certain goal."

In the later history of the Western European states, various forms of corruption and the rise of corrupt relations were reflected not only in historical sources but also in the works of the leading writer philosophers of the time. In particular, it is covered in Shakespeare's "Venetian merchant", "Blood for blood, soul for soul", Dante's "Hell",

"Purifier". Dante expressed the view that the corrupt should be thrown into the darkest and deepest part of hell.

Niccolo Machiavelli, who studied the history and development of corruption, likened it to a cough. but treatment is difficult. □ The truth of these words can be applied to the most widespread forms of corruption in the world today.

In the seventeenth century, Thomas Gobbs said, "Corruption is a growing root of the age, and it is the disregard for any law in the pursuit of all kinds of desires."

All the world's leading religions, first of all, consider it a grave corruption to seek the goodwill of a judge out of all corrupt crimes: see Bible.16: 19); □Do not illegally take possession of one another's property, and do not buy a judge in order to take possession of a part of another's property □ (Qur'an 2:18) and so on.

The U.S. Constitution of 1787 listed bribery as one of the grounds for impeachment of the President of the United States.

The attitude to corruption has existed in the history of our country for a long time, both in historical sources and in the works of thinkers, scientists and writers. For example, in the "Statutes of Temur" of our great ancestor Amir Temur, it is stated that officials should be fair and just in collecting taxes from the people, as well as in collecting taxes from caravans of traders crossing the Silk Road.

The works of Alisher Navoi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Bobir, Ahmad Donish, and Muqumi, thinkers of his time, also criticized the abuse of trust by ordinary people.

Today, the English writer Hilda Hukham describes this situation in her book "Ruler of the Seven Worlds" about our ancestor A.Temur. on the emir, when the people complained that the emir had raised taxes, and the emperor convinced the people that the claim was correct, he punished that emir and confiscated his property and returned it to the people.

Article 3 of the Law on Combating Corruption states that □Corruption is the unlawful use of one's position or position for personal gain or for the benefit of others for material or intangible gain, as well as for such gain. illegal presentation. □

The historical roots of corruption go back a long way, and it is believed that this was due to the custom of giving gifts to tribal chiefs in order to gain a certain position in the tribe. Corruption has a history of several thousand years. Written sources mention corruption during the Sumerian kingdom in BC.

While the Bible says, "Do not accept gifts, for a gift makes the blind see and change the truth," the Qur'an says, Do not bribe your governors with your property. □ That is, □Do not devour one another's wealth in vain. Do not leave it to the rulers sinfully so that you may eat some of the people's wealth knowingly. □ (Surat al-Baqara, 188)

After gaining independence in 1965, Singapore was one of the countries with the highest levels of corruption. However, a number of measures taken against this scourge have led to a reduction in corruption in the country to a minimum. First of all, bureaucratic processes have been simplified here and the independence of the judiciary has been increased (by increasing the income and privileges of judges). At the same time, sanctions for corruption crimes have been tightened, and citizens have been subjected to very large financial sanctions for refusing to cooperate in the investigation of corruption

crimes. Mass "cleansing" was carried out in a number of government agencies, and these processes were broadcast on television throughout the country. All of the factors listed above have made Singapore one of the least corrupt countries in the world in a short period of time. Strict control over the compliance of a civil servant with ethical standards is also one of the important supports in the fight against corruption in the state of Singapore.

On December 9, 2003, a conference was organized in Merida, Mexico to further strengthen ties between countries in the fight against corruption. During the conference, more than 100 countries signed the International Convention against Corruption. The first working day of the conference (December 9) was declared by the UN as Anti-Corruption Day around the world. The adoption and entry into force of this Convention (October 31, 2003) raised the cooperation of countries in the fight against corruption to a new level.

The Convention emphasizes that the development of corruption can be a huge obstacle in the fight against organized crime, terrorism and other negative factors that pose a threat to society.

The purposes of this Convention are:

- adoption and strengthening of highly effective anti-corruption measures;
- expanding, facilitating and supporting international cooperation in the fight against corruption.

The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to the United Nations Convention against Corruption by Law No. ZRU-158 of 7 July 2008, in accordance with which the Prosecutor General's Office, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the State Security Service and the Ministry of Justice designated as bodies that can assist other States Parties in developing and implementing specific measures to prevent corruption.

Today, the fight against corruption in our country is one of the priorities of state policy. In many speeches and speeches, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev says that the fight against indifference, negligence, bribery, corruption, fraud, abuse of office should become the goal of society as a whole, and the main task of law enforcement officials. puts as. The relentless struggle against this evil, which is the cousin of the development of society, is also bearing fruit.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev has identified the formation of an intolerant attitude to corruption in society as one of the main directions of state policy.

Today, I consider it expedient to dwell on the negative consequences of corruption in the life of the state and society.

First, it has a negative impact on the strengthening of democracy and democratic institutions, which play a crucial role in human life, that is, it seriously undermines them.

Second, it leads to the violation of social and legal values such as peace, tranquility, justice, the rule of law, which are the most important factor for the development of society, and destroys the confidence of the general public about their existence.

Third, the violation of the laws of the market economy, the exclusion of healthy competition from the market, creates the basis for the emergence and development of the shadow economy.

Fourth, it leads to the formation of an unhealthy socio-moral environment in society, leading to a violation of the most important legal principles of a democratic state, and how many more such negative consequences can be listed. Now draw your own conclusions ...

Indeed, today, organized criminal structures with corrupt connections, especially those with international connections and operating at the international level, are the most dangerous to the national security of Uzbekistan and are integral to all spheres of public life. are extremely dangerous and complex phenomena.

It should also be remembered that greed, greed, bribery, arrogance, corruption are extremely contagious and dangerous diseases. If not prevented in time, this evil can spread throughout the body of society and destroy it. He first and foremost dismisses the person who is suffering from this disease by eating himself. It destroys his faith, his home in the hereafter. Then it goes on to suck other people, gradually the whole society^[2].

Therefore, it is important today to build a scientific and practical approach to combating corruption, to study the problems in this area, to increase the legal culture and knowledge of the population, especially young people, who play an important role in the prevention of corruption.

Adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On crime prevention" of May 14, 2014 and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" of January 3, 2017, which brought the fight against corruption to a new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan, is important earns.

The Law on Combating Corruption of January 3, 2017 systematically defines the list of entities engaged in combating corruption in Uzbekistan and the activities of these entities.

Department for Combating Tax, Currency Crimes and Money Laundering under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan^[3]. At the same time, anti-corruption activities will be carried out by other government agencies in accordance with the law.

In addition, the organization of anti-corruption activities in the lower and upper chambers of the Oliy Majlis will pave the way for the further prosperity of our society.

In addition, in order to ensure the effective implementation of the provisions of this Law, the timely and quality implementation of measures to prevent corruption in all spheres of society and state life, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2017 "On Combating Corruption" Resolution No. PP-2752 "On measures to implement the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan". This Resolution approved the "State Program on Combating Corruption for 2017-2018" and formed the composition of the Republican Interagency Commission on Combating Corruption.

As a result of the work carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to combat corruption in the first 9 months of 2017, corruption-related crimes decreased by 33% compared to 2016 [4].

In this regard, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2017 No 2833 "On measures to further improve the system of crime prevention and fight against crime" designates every Thursday as "Day of crime prevention" and Particular attention is paid to the implementation of:

- Implement systemic measures aimed at creating a culture of intolerance to crime, improving our legal culture, promoting the law-abiding behavior of citizens, including through the organization of "open days" in communities, law enforcement and other government agencies and organizations;

- organization of mobile receptions of citizens and meetings with representatives of government agencies and organizations on the ground, especially in areas where the criminogenic situation is unfavorable, to discuss in detail the situation with the rule of law and the effectiveness of measures to prevent crime;

- conducting mobile court hearings on socially significant court hearings;

- organization of door-to-door marches in order to study the socio-economic conditions of the population, to identify and eliminate the conditions conducive to crime;

- hearing reports of the heads of government agencies and organizations on measures taken to prevent and combat crime;

- Representatives of government agencies and organizations on special television and radio broadcasts, with the participation of the public to discuss the crime situation on the ground, the causes and conditions of offenses, the results of the work on crime detection and prosecution;

- We can see the implementation of measures to combat crime in the media, including the organization of the publication of articles, comments and other materials on the Internet.

At a press conference dedicated to the results of 2019 by the Main Department for Crime Prevention of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Colonel BEBerdaliev said that as a result of measures taken on Thursday - the Day of Crime Prevention, crimes decreased by 14.6% compared to the same period last year. early detection, as well as the prevention of about 75 thousand offenses. In order to put an end to family conflicts caused by unemployment, about five thousand people were provided with permanent jobs and about one and a half thousand crimes were not committed in the neighborhood, as well as mobile receptions and direct contacts. During the reporting period, about 83,000 citizens received practical assistance. It was also noted that the number of crimes among young people has sharply decreased.

It is no exaggeration to say that this is the result of a new phase in the fight against crime today. We, the youth, are of course holding various events and quizzes at the Institute of World Languages to combat the evils in this area.

Based on the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On crime prevention" dated May 14, 2014, the prevention of corruption offenses is defined as follows:

Korruptsiya related to delinquency prevention, law and order, in accordance with the law and lasting - at least - to identify violations related to the care, korruptsiya bar - shelf, to prevent, identify the causes and conditions giving you the opportunity to o ' To study for the elimination of government agencies and other organizations, as well as citizens associated with korruptsiya law - it is non-public, private, individual and used to viktimologik social, legal, administrative and other measures to understand.

Korruptsiya associated with delinquency special profi - lacquer - mean - korruptsiya-related offenses profi - not to mention lacquer thorn korruptsiyaga of subjects related to the prevention of these types of offenses should be to eliminate the causes and conditions that allow them prone to commit offenses, korruptsiyaga Bo The activity of developing and implementing special measures aimed at identifying and preventing the perpetrators.

The basis for the special prevention of corruption offenses are:

- an increase in corruption-related offenses, as well as the number of categories of persons prone to or have committed such offenses;
- greed, bribery, bribery in business, education, health, utilities and services, housing and communal services, law enforcement in the emergence of risks and threats that negatively affect the social environment, the well-being and health of the population as a result of arrogance.

Today, in cooperation with the Interior Ministry, the Prosecutor's Office and the State Security Service, special operational preventive measures are being taken to identify corrupt and corrupt civil servants and arrest them for crimes. However, at present, the development and implementation of special preventive measures for corruption offenses cannot be considered sufficient. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a set of measures in this regard and clearly define the tasks to be performed by each of the subjects of crime prevention.

Special preventive measures for corruption offenses are carried out within the competence or in cooperation with the above-mentioned state bodies directly involved in the fight against corruption, depending on the criminogenic situation, at the national, regional or district (city) level or in separate small areas, facilities. and activities in enterprises and organizations, as well as the detection of corruption offenses in which these special preventive measures are or may be committed, the prosecution of perpetrators in the manner prescribed by law and the prevention of these offenses.

It should be noted that the implementation of special prevention of corruption offenses is better than punishing those who commit these offenses, that is, as a result of these offenses, citizens, the state and society suffer both economic and moral damage. Therefore, the implementation of special prevention of corruption offenses plays an important role in improving the moral and legal education of members of society, educating them in the spirit of observance and respect for the law.

FOCUS ON THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM OF STANDARDS AGAINST CORRUPTION

The practice of bribery of officials in foreign countries has become an international practice. In some countries, it was even possible to get deductions from your company □s

tax liabilities in exchange for bribes, and this is not surprising, as multinational corporations around the world have already paid bribes to support their businesses.

The high-level corruption scandals associated with this have changed the situation. For example, during an investigation in the mid-1970s. More than 400 American companies have admitted paying bribes and “rewards” totaling more than \$ 300 million to foreign government officials, politicians and political parties. As a result, the U.S. Congress was forced to adopt the Foreign Corrupt Practices Act (1977 - FCPA), which for the first time criminalized bribery of a foreign official.

The adoption of this law has led to more active cooperation of states in discussing the problems of corruption, the need to develop international standards for combating corruption at the global and regional levels.

The anti-corruption legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan consistently implements international standards in the fight against corruption. The fight against corruption is recognized as a priority of national policy. The Anti-Corruption National Action Strategy has been developed and is being implemented in 2 directions of the National Anti-Corruption Plan for 2017-2021. The Law “On Combating Corruption” of January 3, 2017 and a number of Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on this issue in 2017-2020 (which will be discussed below) were adopted.

After the ratification of the United Nations Convention against Corruption on October 31, 2003 by the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2008, a great deal of work has been done in our country to combat corruption. First of all, the international experience was identified in identifying the factors that cause corruption. Below we discuss how the causes and causes of corruption are reflected in international practice.

According to the theoretical analysis of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), the following factors play a major role in the emergence of corruption: the predominance of self-interest and arbitrariness over authority or power, and lack of accountability and transparency.

International legal documents also address the causes of corruption:

- Lack of regulatory framework;
- Weakness of executive discipline;
- low level of legal awareness and legal culture of citizens, etc.

The negative consequences of corruption are as follows:

- 1) seriously undermines the institutions of democracy and human rights;
- 2) leads to the violation of social and legal values such as peace, tranquility, justice, the rule of law in society;
- 3) destroys public confidence in the government;
- 4) violation of the laws of a market economy, creates the basis for the emergence and development of the shadow economy;
- 5) leads to a violation of important principles of a democratic state, and so on.

Today, a system of international standards for combating corruption has been formed, some of which are of a recommendatory nature and have been developed by a number of international organizations established for this purpose. **The system of such organizations includes:**

1. United Nations;
2. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development;
3. Commonwealth of Independent States;
- 4 The Egmont Group is an association of financial intelligence units from 155 countries;
5. Transparency International;
6. The FATF includes the Financial Action Task Force, a group that develops financial measures against money laundering.

There are also a number of conventions of the UN, the Council of the European Union in the fight against corruption.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has ratified some of them in the fight against corruption. In particular, **in order to organize the fight against corruption in accordance with international standards:**

- On July 7, 2008, Uzbekistan adopted the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-158 "On Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the United Nations Convention against Corruption (New York, October 31, 2003)";

- In March 2010, Uzbekistan joined the Istanbul Plan for Combating Corruption (September 10, 2003) adopted within the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.

The United Nations Convention **against Corruption of 31 October 2003 consists of an** introduction and 8 chapters and 71 articles:

Chapter 1 (1-4) General Provisions,

Chapter 2 (5-14) Measures to Prevent Corruption,

Chapter 3 (15-42) Crime and Law Enforcement Activities,

Chapter 4 (43-50) International Cooperation,

Chapter 5 (51-59) Measures for the return of assets,

Chapter 6 (60-62) Technical Support and Information Exchange,

Chapter 7 (63-64) Implementation Mechanisms,

Chapter 8 (65-71) sets out the Final Provisions.

Transparency International has released its latest report on the **Corruption Perceptions Index 2019**, an international non-governmental organization. According to the report, the Republic of Uzbekistan rose 5 places with 25 points and took 153rd place. Among the Eastern European countries with the highest average in the world, Georgia scored 56 points, Belarus with 45 points and Montenegro with 45 points. At the same time, from Central Asian countries: Turkmenistan scored 19 points, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan - 25 points.

It should be noted that since 2012, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan and the Republic of Uzbekistan have significantly improved their positions in the Corruption Perceptions Index.

According to Transparency International's 2019 report, corruption is almost non-existent in the following countries: Denmark and New Zealand with 87 points, Finland with 86 points and Finland with 85 points. Singapore, Sweden and Switzerland took 4th place and showed positive results.

Since 1995, the Corruption Perceptions Index has been rated on a scale of 0 (highest) to 100 (lowest) based on the assessments of experts and entrepreneurs in determining the level of corruption in the public sector in all countries of the world. The index is also assessed by collecting various sources of corruption data produced by the World Bank, the World Justice Project, the African Development Bank, the Economist Intelligence Unit and other independent and well-known institutions.

In the current era of globalization, a complex environment in which regional and interstate integration is accelerating, corruption poses a number of problems in all countries and threatens to tear society apart. Therefore, today we cannot say that any state, big or small, rich or poor, powerful or weak, is a zone free of corruption. According to the United Nations and the International Monetary Fund, the global economy suffers from \$ 1.5-2.6 trillion a year due to corruption.

That is why our country is waging a fierce and uncompromising fight against corruption. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Combating Corruption", as well as the establishment of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption and the approval of the State Anti-Corruption Program have effectively implemented a number of measures to prevent corruption in the country. ensured the implementation. For example, in a short period of time, five normative and legal acts on improving the legal mechanisms for combating corruption, including the Law "On Dissemination and Use of Legal Information" and the Law "On Administrative Procedures" were adopted. , The Law on Public Oversight, and the Law on Public Procurement.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-419 of January 3, 2017 "On Combating Corruption" was an important step in this direction.

In this document:

- Definition of the terms corruption, conflict of interest;
- anti-corruption, competent authorities and their functions,
- responsibility for corruption,
- Raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population in the fight against corruption;
- All important aspects, such as international anti-corruption cooperation.

For example, in Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 3, 2017 "On Combating Corruption":

"Corruption is the unlawful use of one's position or position for personal or material gain, as well as the unlawful provision of such benefits."

On February 2, 2017, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to implement the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan" On Combating Corruption "was published, in which:

- State Anti-Corruption Program for 2017-2018,
- The composition of the interdepartmental commission on combating corruption and
- The Charter of the Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption was approved.

On May 27, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5729 "On measures to further improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. The decree is a logical continuation of consistent efforts in this direction, the main purpose of which is to further increase the effectiveness of the anti-corruption system in our country, create a favorable investment and business environment, enhance and strengthen the country's positive image in the international arena. The decree defines the tasks consisting of 35 items in 4 directions, which are:

- I. Raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, the formation of an intolerant attitude to corruption in society;
- II. Implement measures to prevent corruption in all spheres of state and public life;
- III. Timely detection of corruption offenses, their elimination, elimination of possible causes, conditions and consequences, ensuring the principle of inevitability of liability for corruption offenses;
- IV. International cooperation in the fight against corruption.

This Decree adopted the State Anti-Corruption Program for 2019-2020 and approved the updated composition of the Republican Interagency Commission on Combating Corruption.

The decree also identified priorities of state policy in the fight against corruption. In particular, further strengthening the independence of the judiciary, eliminating the conditions for any unlawful influence on judges, the formation of a civil service system based on a transparent procedure for the selection, appointment and promotion of civil servants, Gradual introduction of the system of declaration of income of civil servants, introduction of effective organizational and legal mechanisms to protect those who report corruption-related offenses, strengthening intolerance of corruption in society, increasing the accountability and transparency of government agencies and organizations, citizenship issues such as ensuring genuine freedom of public institutions, the media and involving them in the preparation, implementation and monitoring of anti-corruption measures are one of them.

Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" defines the state bodies engaged in combating corruption, which include:

- Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Anti-corruption activities are also carried out by other government agencies in accordance with the law.

The Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption has been established to coordinate the activities of bodies and organizations involved in the fight against corruption. The formation and procedure of this Interdepartmental Commission shall be determined by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in the regions and in the city of Tashkent, the procedure for establishing territorial interagency commissions to combat corruption is established in the manner prescribed by law.

The main tasks of the Interagency Commission are:

- organization of development and implementation of state programs and other programs in the field of combating corruption;
- coordination and cooperation of anti-corruption bodies and organizations involved in the fight against corruption;
- to raise the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, to form an intolerant attitude to corruption in society
- organization of development and implementation of measures;
- Ensuring the effectiveness of measures to prevent, detect, curb corruption offenses, eliminate their consequences, as well as the causes and conditions that allow them;
- collection and analysis of information on the state and trends of corruption;
- monitoring the implementation of measures to combat corruption, assessing the effectiveness of existing organizational, practical and legal mechanisms in this area;
- preparation of proposals for the improvement of anti-corruption legislation and work in this area;
- coordination of the activities of territorial interdepartmental commissions.

Today, we are active in the fight against Summers Korrupstiyaga manipulate them takidlaganlaridek, the head of the future smile allbata we used in today's papers, all the installation of these young adults, and to fight against all the odds for this call.

[1] Living on the basis of high spirituality and the rule of law, the development of a culture of loyalty to the people, justice, honesty and good manners: the website of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

[2] See *Karimov I. A.* May our Motherland remain free and prosperous. - T. 2. - T., 1996. - 200-b.

[3] Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the fight against corruption / official publication / Uzbekistan. «Adolat», 2017. - 80 p.

[4] *Jalolov Sh.R.* Bribery is the basis of corruption crimes // Bulletin of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - № 4. 56-61 p.

REFERENCE:

1. Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (approved by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2021-XII of September 22, 1994);
2. United Nations Convention against Corruption, 9 December 2003;
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-419 of January 3, 2017 "On Combating Corruption";

4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-2752 of February 2, 2017 on measures to implement the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption";

5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5729 of May 27, 2019 "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan";

6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6013 of 29 March 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan". According to one appendix to the decree, the "Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan" will be established.

7. Living on the basis of high spirituality and the rule of law, the development of loyalty to the people, justice, honesty and problem culture: Website of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

8. Jalolov Sh.R. The basis of bribery and corruption crimes // Bulletin of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2017. N. 4. 56-61B.

